

Evaluating the efficacy of 30 mcg Clonidine versus 10 mcg Dexmedetomidine given intrathecal as an adjuvant to Bupivacaine in Orthopaedic Surgery: A Prospective, Interventional, Randomized Clinical Study

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Abstract:

Background: Addition of adjuvants to routinely used intrathecal drugs is cornerstone in safe and effective prolongation of analgesia. Alpha 2 agonists are considered best drugs as adjuvants, but there is limited literature about its use in orthopedic surgeries and further side effects.

Aims: To evaluate the efficacy of 30 mcg clonidine versus 10 mcg Dexmedetomidine given intrathecal as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in orthopaedic surgeries.

Methods: This prospective, interventional, double-blind, randomized, clinical study was conducted from Jan 2023 to August 2023. 90 patients, ASA physical status I and II, aged 18-60 y of either sex, undergoing elective orthopaedic surgeries were randomly allocated into two groups: Group A: (0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg + clonidine 30 µg) (n=45); Group B: (0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg + dexmedetomidine 10 µg) (n=45). The parameters assessed included the onset of sensory and motor blockades, mean sensory regression through two-segment comparison, duration of motor block, timing of rescue analgesia, surgery duration, VAS pain scores, and any adverse events, all of which were recorded and analysed statistically.

Results: On comparison between both groups, Group B (10mcg Dexmedetomidine) showed statistically significantly faster mean sensory & motor blockage onset, prolonged duration of sensory & motor block, and improved quality of intraoperative anaesthesia with good hemodynamic stability and minimal side effects as compared to Group A (30mcg Clonidine).

Conclusion: Addition of 10 mcg dexmedetomidine with 0.5% hyperbaric 12.5 mg bupivacaine in intrathecal anaesthesia in orthopaedic surgery resulted in significantly early onset of sensory & motor block and prolongation of durations of motor and sensory block as compared to 30 mcg Clonidine with 0.5% hyperbaric 12.5 mg bupivacaine.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine, Clonidine, Bupivacaine, Orthopaedic Surgeries.

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Introduction

Intrathecal anesthesia is a cornerstone technique in orthopaedic surgeries, offering reliable sensory and motor blockade with minimal systemic interference. The efficacy of intrathecal anesthesia primarily depends on the local anaesthetic used, with bupivacaine being one of the most commonly employed agents due to its long duration of action and favourable safety profile.[1] However, to further enhance the quality and duration of anesthesia, as well as postoperative analgesia, various adjuvants are frequently added to local anaesthetics. Among these, α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonists such as clonidine and dexmedetomidine have gained significant attention for their synergistic effects with bupivacaine and their

ability to improve patient outcomes.[2]

Clonidine, a partial α_2 -adrenergic agonist, is widely recognized for its sedative, anxiolytic, and analgesic properties. When used as an intrathecal adjuvant to bupivacaine, clonidine not only prolongs the duration of sensory and motor blockades but also enhances the quality of postoperative analgesia. Its mechanism of action involves hyperpolarization of nerve fibers and inhibition of nociceptive signal transmission, resulting in reduced pain perception. Furthermore, clonidine has been found to exert a dose-dependent effect, balancing efficacy and side effects when used at optimal doses such as 30 mcg. [3]

Dexmedetomidine, a highly selective and potent α_2 -adrenergic agonist, offers even greater receptor specificity compared to clonidine. This increased selectivity contributes to its superior analgesic and sedative properties. Intrathecal administration of dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant has been associated with a faster onset and longer duration of sensory and motor blockade, along with improved hemodynamic stability and reduced requirement for postoperative analgesics. Despite its smaller dose requirement, typically around 10 mcg, dexmedetomidine achieves significant clinical effects, making it an attractive option for enhancing the efficacy of spinal anesthesia.[4]

While both clonidine and dexmedetomidine have been extensively studied as intrathecal adjuvants, direct comparisons between these two agents, particularly in the context of orthopaedic surgeries, are limited. Understanding their relative efficacy and safety when added to bupivacaine is essential for optimizing anaesthetic protocols and improving patient care. The choice of adjuvant can significantly impact the duration of analgesia, patient comfort, intraoperative conditions, and the risk of adverse effects, making it a critical consideration in clinical practice.[5]

This prospective randomised study aims to evaluate the efficacy of 30 mcg clonidine versus 10 mcg dexmedetomidine as intrathecal adjuvants to bupivacaine in orthopaedic surgeries. By comparing their effects on the onset and duration of sensory and motor blockades, quality of intraoperative anaesthesia, and postoperative pain relief, this research seeks to provide evidence-based guidance for anaesthetic management. Additionally, potential side effects and hemodynamic stability will be assessed to ensure the safety and tolerability of these adjuvants. The findings of this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of how these agents can be utilized to enhance the overall anaesthetic experience, ultimately benefiting both patients and clinicians in orthopaedic surgical settings

Material & Methods

This prospective, interventional, double-blind, randomized, clinical study was conducted, from Jan 2023 to August 2023. Ninety patients, ASA physical status I and II, aged 18-60 y of either sex, undergoing elective orthopaedic surgeries were enrolled in the study. Exclusion criteria included patient refusal, hypersensitivity to the drugs being evaluated, Body Mass Index (BMI) more than 40 kg/m², pregnancy, significant comorbid conditions like uncontrolled hypertension, congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction in the past 6 months, heart block, fixed cardiac output lesions. Cases which needed intraoperative conversion to general anaesthesia were also excluded.

A written informed consent was taken from all patients and approval from the institutional ethical committee was sought.

90 patients were randomly allocated using sealed envelope technique into two groups:

Group A: (0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg + clonidine 30 μ g) (n=45)

Group B: (0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg + dexmedetomidine 10 μ g) (n=45)

A detailed pre-anaesthetic checkup was conducted a day prior to the planned surgery and included an elaborate history of current and coexisting illnesses, detailed general, systemic, airway examinations and all pertinent investigations as per institutional protocol were conducted and reviewed. All patients were explained about Visual Analog Scale (VAS). Tablet alprazolam 0.25 mg and tablet ranitidine 150 mg were given as premedication night before and on the morning of surgery to all patients.

After applying standard monitors such as non-invasive blood pressure (NIBP), heart rate (HR), peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) and electrocardiography, initial baseline data was recorded. Intravenous (IV) access was secured and crystalloid solution 15 ml/kg was infused to each patient prior to SAB. The SAB was performed in the standard method, and the study drugs were injected into the spinal theca.

Pain was assessed using VAS hourly for the first 4 h, then 4 hourly for the next 8 h, and at 24 h postoperatively.

Tramadol 1.5 mg/kg was administered slowly via IV as a rescue analgesic when the VAS exceeded 4. The timing of the first rescue analgesic and the total number of rescue analgesics given over a 24-hour period were recorded. All time durations were calculated with the completion of the IT injection marked as time zero. The times for skin incision and skin closure were also noted, allowing for the calculation of the surgery duration in minutes.

The Ramsay sedation score (RSS) was utilized to evaluate sedation levels. Patients' sedation scores were assessed hourly for the first 4 hours after surgery, and then again at 8, 12, and 24 hours following the spinal injection. During the postoperative period, the Bromage score and sensory level were evaluated every 15 minutes until recovery to Bromage 0 and two-segment sensory regression (TSSR), respectively. The parameters assessed included the onset of sensory and motor block, mean sensory regression through two-segment comparison, duration of motor block, timing of rescue analgesia, surgery duration, VAS pain scores, and any adverse events, all of which were recorded and analyzed statistically.

Statistical analysis

Data was collected and compiled using Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. The continuous data were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation. Frequency, percentage, means, and standard deviations (SD) were calculated for continuous variables, while ratios and proportions were determined for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant. To assess the significance of two

means, the Student's t-test was employed.

Results

In this prospective randomised study, 90 patients who were undergoing elective orthopaedic surgeries were enrolled, out of which 53 were males and 37 were females. There were no statistically significant differences in the sociodemographics of the patients and duration of surgery between the Group A and Group B ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Shows the comparison between the study parameters in Group A and Group B

Parameters Assessed	Group A	Group B	P value
Sensory onset duration (min)	1.4 \pm 0.6	1.1 \pm 0.5	P<0.05 significant
Motor onset duration (min)	1.7 \pm 0.4	1.2 \pm 0.6	P<0.05 significant
Mean sensory regression by two segment comparison (min)	135 \pm 9.8	172.45 \pm 24.39	P<0.05 significant
Duration of motor blockage (min)	280.4 \pm 25.4	339.7 \pm 35.7	P<0.05 significant
Time of rescue analgesia (min)	347.6 \pm 29.7	370.8 \pm 39.6	P<0.05 significant
Duration of surgery(min)	103.92 \pm 39.29	108.58 \pm 27.09	p>0.05 non significant
VAS Pain scores	4.6 \pm 0.5	4.4 \pm 0.6	P<0.05 significant

Table 2: Shows the Adverse events

Adverse events	N(%)	N(%)	P value
Bradycardia	2(6.66%)	3(10%)	p>0.05 non significant
Hypotension	4(13.33%)	5(16.66)	p>0.05 non significant
Nausea	0	2(6.66%)	p>0.05 non significant
Shivering	0	0	p>0.05 non significant

The mean sensory onset and mean motor onset was shorter in Group B which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean sensory regression by two segment comparison was significantly shorter in Group A as compared to Group B ($p < 0.05$). The duration of motor blockage & time of rescue analgesia was significantly higher in Group B ($p < 0.05$). The VAS pain score levels were lower in Group B which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). (Table 1) The adverse events, bradycardia, hypotension, nausea were noted to be higher in Group B which were statistically non significant ($p > 0.05$). (Table 2)

Discussion

One of the primary objectives of anaesthesia is the alleviation of pain. With their technical expertise and pharmacological understanding, anaesthesiologists are uniquely positioned to manage pain during both the intraoperative and postoperative phases. The aim of effective postoperative analgesia is to achieve long-lasting, continuous pain relief while minimizing adverse effects. Consequently, the addition of intrathecal agents to local anaesthetics provides a reliable and predictable approach to extend the duration of anaesthesia and ensure prolonged postoperative analgesia. The spinal anaesthesia technique, noted for its simplicity and convenience, has gained widespread acceptance.[6]

Various agents, including epinephrine, phenylephrine, adenosine, magnesium sulfate, sodium bicarbonate, neostigmine, and alpha-2 agonists, have been employed as adjuncts to local anaesthetics to enhance the duration of spinal anaesthesia. Among these, clonidine, an α_2 agonist, is commonly administered via oral, intrathecal, and intravenous routes to extend the effects of spinal anaesthesia.[7] Dexmedetomidine, which exhibits a tenfold greater affinity for α_2 adrenergic receptors compared to clonidine and significantly reduced α_1 effects, has emerged as a more effective hypnotic, sedative, and analgesic agent, characterized by a more advantageous pharmacodynamic profile. It appears to be a valuable adjunct in regional anaesthesia and analgesia, offering improved hemodynamic stability and minimal side effects.[8]

In the present study, Group A patients were administered 30 mcg clonidine as an adjuvant to 12.5 mg bupivacaine and in Group B were administered 10 mcg Dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to 12.5 mg bupivacaine. In both Group A and Group B, adequately faster mean sensory blockage onset and mean motor blockage onset was observed. The duration of sensory & motor blockage onset was statistically significantly shorter in Group B ($p < 0.05$). This is in accordance with the Bhatia et al 2020 study wherein 60 adult patients received subarachnoid block either with Injection Bupivacaine (15mg) with clonidine

(30mg) or Injection Bupivacaine (15mg) with Dexmedetomidine (10mg) and concluded that Clonidine and Dexmedetomidine prolonged duration of sensory and motor block of Bupivacaine, But Dexmedetomidine was more appropriate as it provides better VAS score (quality) and longer duration of postoperative analgesia than clonidine.[9]

Mean onset time of motor blockade was earlier in group dexmedetomidine which was significant and was in agreement with the study conducted by Suthar et al 2015[10], Naaz et al 2016.[11]

In the present study, time taken for regression of sensory blockade by 2 segments was earlier in group A and more in group B ($p < 0.05$). Duration of analgesia was prolonged in both the groups with statistically significantly longer duration of analgesia observed in Group B i.e. Dexmedetomidine group. This could be attributed to that both Dexmedetomidine and clonidine produces analgesia by activating α_2 adrenoceptors in the spinal cord by reducing transmission of adrenoceptors nociceptive signals. This could be attributed to the fact that the local anaesthetics act by blocking sodium channels, whereas α_2 adrenergic agonists act by binding to pre synaptic C fibres and post synaptic dorsal horn neurons. Intrathecal α_2 adrenergic agonists produce anaesthesia by depressing the release of C fibre transmitters and by hyperpolarisation of post synaptic dorsal horn neurons. This antinociceptive effect may explain the prolongation of sensory block while prolongation of the motor block of spinal anaesthetics may result from the binding of α_2 adrenergic agonists to motor neurons in dorsal horn.[12]

In the present study, duration of analgesia was significantly prolonged in Dexmedetomidine group as compared to clonidine ($p < 0.05$). Also, in the present study, VAS pain score levels were lower in Group B than Group A which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). (Table 1) The time taken for rescue analgesics were statistically significantly prolonged in Group B. The adverse events, bradycardia, hypotension, nausea were noted to be higher in Group B than Group A which were statistically non significant ($p > 0.05$). (Table 2) Similar results shown by Suthar et al 2015[10], Naaz et al 2016[11], Akhter Met al 2017.[4]

Conclusion

Thus, Addition of 10mcg dexmedetomidine as compared to 30mcg clonidine with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 12.5 mg in intrathecal anaesthesia in orthopaedic surgeries resulted in significantly early onset of sensory and motor block, prolongation of duration of motor and sensory block, improved quality of intraoperative and post operative analgesia with good

hemodynamic stability and minimal side effects.

References

- Joshi R, Latha N, Ramesh J, et al B422 A comparison of spinal anesthesia characteristics between hyperbaric ropivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine in subarachnoid block for lower segment caesarean section: a prospective randomised study. *Regional Anesthesia & Pain Medicine* 2022;47:A283-A284.
- Kamel I, Ahmed MF, Sethi A. Regional anesthesia for orthopaedic procedures: What orthopaedic surgeons need to know. *World J Orthop.* 2022 Jan 18;13(1):11-35. doi: 10.5312/wjo.v13.i1.11. PMID: 35096534; PMCID: PMC8771411.
- Agarwal D, Chopra M, Mohta M, Sethi AK. Clonidine as an adjuvant to hyperbaric bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia in elderly patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. *Saudi J Anaesth.* 2014 Apr;8(2):209-14. doi: 10.4103/1658-354X.130720. PMID: 24843334; PMCID: PMC4024678.
- Mehmooda Akhter, Abdul Waheed Mir, Bilal Ahmad, Faroz Ahmad, Suhail Sidiq, Mohamad Akbar Shah, Sofi Khalid. Dexmedetomidine as an adjunct to spinal anesthesia in urological procedures. *International Journal of Contemporary Medical Research* 2017;4(1):154-158.
- Ganesh M, Krishnamurthy D. A Comparative Study of Dexmedetomidine and Clonidine as an Adjuvant to Intrathecal Bupivacaine in Lower Abdominal Surgeries. *Anesth Essays Res.* 2018 Apr-Jun;12(2):539-545. doi: 10.4103/aer.AER_54_18. PMID: 29962631; PMCID: PMC6020565.
- Halvadia S, Patel D. Comparative study of different doses of dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to intrathecal hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. *Anaesth. pain & intensive care* 2019;23(2):198-203
- Asano T, Dohi S, Ohta S, Shimonaka H, Lida H. Antinociception by epidural and systemic α_2 adrenoreceptor agonists and their binding affinity in rat spinal cord and brain. *Anesth Analg.* 2000;90:400-7.
- Al-Ghanem SM, Massad IM, Al-Mustafa MM, Al-Zaben RK, Qudaisat IY et al. Effect of adding dexmedetomidine versus fentanyl to intrathecal bupivacaine on spinal block characteristics in gynecological procedure. *Am JA Appl Sci.* 2009;6:882-7.
- Bhatia U V, Dave S, Hudda R R, A comparison of intrathecal low dose Dexmedetomidine and clonidine as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in patients undergoing gynecological surgeries. *Indian J Clin Anaesth* 2020;7(1):147-152

10. Suthar O, Sethi P, Sharma UD. Comparison of dexmedetomidine and clonidine as an adjuvant to intrathecal bupivacaine in lower limb surgery: A randomised, double-blind, placebo controlled trial. *Anaesth Pain & Intensive Care* 2015;18(2):149-154.
11. S Naaz J Bandey - Ozair A Asghar Optimal Dose of intrathecal Dexmedetomidine in lower abdominal surgeries in average Indian adult. *J Clin Diagnostic Res* 2016;10(9):13-18.
12. Ganesh M, Krishnamurthy D. A Comparative Study of Dexmedetomidine and Clonidine as an Adjuvant to Intrathecal Bupivacaine in Lower Abdominal Surgeries. *Anesth Essays Res.* 2018 Apr-Jun;12(2):539-545. doi: 10.4103/aer.AER_54_18. PMID: 29962631; PMCID: PMC6020565.